

A FINITE DIFFERENCE METHOD FOR THE SOLUTION OF THIRD ORDER BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS IN ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an efficient finite difference method to solve third order boundary value problems. Analysis proves that the proposed method have at least quadratic convergence. Numerical results confirm the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Boundary Value Problems, Finite Difference, Taylor series, Row Sum Norm, Maximum Error.

1. Introduction

Third-order differential equations arise in many modelling problems like aeroelasticity, beam deflection theory, electromagnetic waves, theory of thin film flow.

In this paper, we study an effective numerical technique based on finite differences to solve third order boundary value problems(BVPs) of the following type:

$$u''' = f(x, u), a \leq x \leq b \quad (1.1)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$u''(a) = \alpha, u(b) = \beta, u'(b) = \gamma \quad (1.2)$$

where the α , β and γ are arbitrary constants.

The discussion on the existence, uniqueness and convergence of the solution of problem 1.1 can be found in the literature [1], [12], [3], [6]. We wont mention the conditions on the existence and uniqueness of the solution to problem 1.1.

We assume the existence and uniqueness of the solution to problem 1.1. We also assume that problem 1.1 is well posed.

This article is arranged in the following order. In section 2, we propose the finite difference method. In section 3, we discuss the convergence of the proposed method. In section 4, we illustrate the method with examples and finally in section 5 we present the performance of our proposed method.

2. The Difference method

To find an approximation to the solution of the problem 1.1, we discretize the domain $[a, b]$ into N equal subintervals each of size $h = \frac{b-a}{N}$:

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N-1} < x_N = b \quad (2.1)$$

where the nodes are given by $x_i = a + ih, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

We want to determine the numerical approximation of the true solution $u(x)$ of the problem 1.1 at the nodal point

$$x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Let u_i and f_i denote the numerical approximations of $u(x)$ and $f(x, u(x))$ at $x = x_i, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$ which allows us to write the boundary value problem 1.1 at node $x = x_i$ as written as

$$u_i''' = f_i, a \leq x_i \leq b \quad (2.2)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$u_0'' = \alpha, u_N = \beta, u_N' = \gamma.$$

We define the nodes as

$$x_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}} = x_i \pm \frac{h}{2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$$

and denote the solution of the problem 2.2 at $x_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}}$ by

$$u_{i \pm \frac{1}{2}}.$$

Using the method of undetermined coefficients and Taylor's series expansion [7, 8, 9], we get the following scheme:

$$\begin{aligned} u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - 2u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{3}{2}} &= h^2 u_{i-1}'' + \frac{h^3}{24} (25u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}''' + 11u_{i+\frac{1}{2}}''') + T_i, i = 1 \\ -u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 3u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - 3u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{3}{2}} &= \frac{h^3}{2} (u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}''' + u_{i+\frac{1}{2}}''') + T_i, 2 \leq i \leq N - 2 \\ u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} - 3u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + 2u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} &= hu_{i+1}' + \frac{h^3}{48} (21u_{i-\frac{3}{2}}''' - 67u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}''') + T_i, i = N - 1 \\ -2u_{i-\frac{5}{2}} + 5u_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} &= 8u_i - 5hu_i' + \frac{h^3}{24} (25u_{i-\frac{3}{2}}''' + 30u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}''') + T_i, i = N \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

where

$$T_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

is the truncation error.

After neglecting the truncation errors T_i at the nodes $x_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, in 2.3, we obtain a system of $N \times N$ equations in the unknowns $u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}$, which may be linear or non-linear according as $f(x, u)$ is linear or non-linear.

Using the values $u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}$, we compute the values $u_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ according to the second-order approximation

$$u_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(3u_{i+\frac{3}{2}} - u_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + u_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq N - 1 \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

3. Convergence Analysis

Let $U_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, \dots, N$, denote the true solution of the problem 1.1 at the $x_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, \dots, N$ and let \mathbf{U} be the column vector

$$\mathbf{U} = [U_{i-\frac{1}{2}}] \quad (3.1)$$

Also let, \mathbf{u} be the column vector consisting of the approximations $u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}$ at the nodes $x_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, \dots, N$,

$$\mathbf{u} = [u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}] \quad (3.2)$$

and the errors at the nodes $x_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, \dots, N$ be denoted by

$$\epsilon_{i-\frac{1}{2}} = U_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (3.3)$$

and the error vector in column form be denoted by

$$\mathbf{e} = [\epsilon_{i-\frac{1}{2}}] = [U_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}] \quad (3.4)$$

Then, we have the following equations

$$\mathbf{AU} = \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{t} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathbf{Au} = \mathbf{b} \quad (3.6)$$

where the $N \times N$ matrix \mathbf{A} and column vectors \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{t} are given by

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -2 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & & & & 0 \\ -1 & 3 & -3 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & & & \\ 0 & -1 & 3 & -3 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & & \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 3 & -3 & 1 & 0 & \dots & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 3 & -3 & 1 & 0 & \dots & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \dots & \\ \vdots & & & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \dots & \\ & & & & & -1 & 3 & -3 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & & & & \dots & 0 & 0 & 1 & -3 & 2 \\ & & & & \dots & 0 & 0 & -2 & 5 & 5 \end{bmatrix}_{N \times N} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = [b_i] \quad (3.8)$$

$$\mathbf{t} = [T_i] \quad (3.9)$$

and the b_i 's and T_i 's are given by

$$b_i = \begin{cases} h^2\alpha + \frac{h^3}{24}(25f_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + 11f_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = 1 \\ \frac{h^3}{2}(f_{i-\frac{1}{2}} + f_{i+\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, 2 \leq i \leq N - 2 \\ h\gamma + \frac{h^3}{48}(21f_{i-\frac{3}{2}} - 67f_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = N - 1 \\ 8\beta - 5h\gamma + \frac{h^3}{24}(25f_{i-\frac{3}{2}} + 30f_{i-\frac{1}{2}}) + T_i, i = N \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$T_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} \text{ if } i = 1, \\ \frac{1}{240}h^7u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(7)} \text{ if } 2 \leq i \leq N - 2, \\ -\frac{809}{1920}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} \text{ if } i = N - 1, \\ -\frac{7}{384}h^5u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}^{(5)} \text{ if } i = N \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

The matrix \mathbf{A} is nonsingular [4, 5] and its inverse $\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \mathbf{B} = [b_{ij}]$ is given by

$$b_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{8} & \text{if } i = N, j = 1, \dots, N \\ \frac{1}{8} & \text{if } i = 1, \dots, N - 1, j = N \\ \frac{(2(N-i)+1)^2}{8} & \text{if } i = 1, \dots, N - 2, j \leq i \\ \frac{(2(N-i)+1)^2}{8} & \text{if } i = N - 1, N, j = 1, \dots, N - 2 \\ \vdots & \end{cases} \quad (3.12)$$

and

$$\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| = \frac{8N^3 - 16N^2 + 15N - 6}{24} \quad (3.13)$$

Here $\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|$ denotes the maximum row sum norm of \mathbf{A}^{-1} .

Now,

$$\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| \leq \frac{N^3}{3} \quad (3.14)$$

From equations 3.5 and 3.6, we have

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{t} \quad (3.15)$$

which gives

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{t} \quad (3.16)$$

Therefore,

$$\|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\| \|\mathbf{t}\| \quad (3.17)$$

where $\|\mathbf{t}\|$ is the maximum norm of \mathbf{t} .

If we let,

$$M = \max_{a \leq x \leq b} |u^{(5)}(x)| \quad (3.18)$$

Then

$$\|\mathbf{t}\| \leq Mh^5 \quad (3.19)$$

Hence

$$\|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \frac{N^3 M h^5}{3} = \frac{(b-a)^3 M h^5}{3h^3} = \frac{M(b-a)^3}{3} h^2 \quad (3.20)$$

which shows that the our proposed scheme 2.3, 2.4 has second order convergence.

4. Numerical Examples

The following problems illustrate the performance of our method. We compute the maximum absolute error MAE in the true solution $u(x)$, namely:

$$\text{MAE} = \max_{0 \leq i \leq N} |u(x_i) - u_i|$$

All the computations were performed on Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS GNU linux operating system with IDLE 3.8.10 running Python version 3.8.10 on Intel® Core™ i5-9400 CPU @ 2.90GHz × 6 PC.

Example 4.1. Consider the linear model problem in [10] given by:

$$u''' - xu(x) = (x^3 - 2x^2 - 5x - 3) \exp(x), 0 \leq x \leq 1 \quad (4.1)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = 0, u(1) = 0, u'(1) = -\exp(1) \quad (4.2)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = x(1-x)\exp(x) \quad (4.3)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below

N	MAE
128	8.150736478892279e-05
256	2.0557217413813555e-05
512	5.161967603378552e-06
1024	1.2933322996243161e-06
2048	3.2368860043946283e-07
4096	8.096661511538226e-08

Example 4.2. Consider the linear model problem in [11] given by:

$$u''' + u(x) = (x^2 - 6x - 1) \sin(x) + (7 - x^2) \cos(x), 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (4.4)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = 0, u(1) = 0, u'(1) = 2\sin(1) \quad (4.5)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = (x^2 - 1)\sin(x) \quad (4.6)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below:

N	MAE
128	3.0204368352604316e-05
256	7.55068418839544e-06
512	1.8876175097159997e-06
1024	4.71897596415749e-07
2048	1.1797358473453201e-07
4096	2.9493265135682734e-08

Example 4.3. Consider the nonlinear model problem in [12] given by:

$$u''' + 2\exp(-3u(x)) = 4(1+x)^{-3}, 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (4.7)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$u''(0) = -1, u(1) = \ln(2), u'(1) = \frac{1}{2} \quad (4.8)$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \ln(1+x) \quad (4.9)$$

The MAE computed by method 2.3 for different values of N are given below:

N	MAE
128	2.2417700782846953e-05
256	5.662842074857788e-06
512	1.4230859950213962e-06
1024	3.5669952002108547e-07
2048	8.92905674886816e-08
4096	2.2330040715915107e-08

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have proposed a numerical method to solve third order boundary value problems having quadratic convergence. We have estimated the error involved. We have also given several numerical examples which confirms our claim.

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